

Establishing a Comprehensive Fisheries Diversity Checklist in Cox's Bazar Coastal Region: Exploring New Potential for Mariculture Development in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Studying fish ecology is crucial for understanding and maintaining aquatic ecosystems. In this regard, this study was carried out in the Chowfaldandi Khal, a subtropical river catchment in Bangladesh, to study the composition and diversity of fish species. The sampling was conducted from March 2022 to January 2023, covering four temporal segments in three selected stations representing the upper, middle, and lower streams of the catchment. A total of 4208 individual fish were collected, including 40 species of fish belonging to 25 families. *Glossogobius giuris* (10.43%), *Acentrogobius viridipunctatus* (6.69%), *Ambassis dussumieri* (6.54%), *Taenioides anguillaris* (5.57%), *Escualosa thoracata* (4.87%), *Awaous grammepomus* (4.73%), and *Chanda nama* (4.71%) were found to be the most dominant species. The Shannon-Weiner diversity index (H'), Margalef richness index (d), Pielou's evenness index (J'), and Simpson dominance index (c) ranged from 3.16-3.43, 5.89-6.27, 0.88-0.95, and 0.91-0.97, respectively. Overall spatiotemporal fish diversity indices and their composition, including some marine juveniles, clearly indicate the suitability of the site as breeding, spawning, and nursing grounds. This catchment is important for the local estuarine aquatic ecosystem and local fisheries. However, there is no record of previous studies for this catchment. So, the current study may serve as a reference for future exploration, mariculture establishment, and management strategy development in this site and other coastal regions of Bangladesh.

Keywords: Fish diversity checklist; Fish composition; Mariculture development; Bangladesh.